
ENYONG CREEK WATER QUALITY ALONG ITS REACH WITH CONSIDERATION FOR
DOMESTIC AND IRRIGATION USES

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ABSTRACT

The quality of Enyong Creek water was investigated using standard methods in day time with active human activities with 18 samples replicated in October to March being the dry season when irrigation is practicable. The nutrients and the trace element contents were generally low in the water samples and in most cases were below the highest desirable or permissible limits set by the World Health Organization (WHO) for drinking water standards. For irrigation purposes, all the samples were found to be of excellent quality, and are therefore put in low salinity and low sodium hazard class (CI – SI) using USDA classification system. The minimum quantity available would consider the use for fishing and water transportation to arrive at how much irrigable area can be accommodated without making the basin a closed water resource system in dry season.

KEYWORDS: conjunctive use, irrigation, safe drinkingwater, salinity, sodium hazard, Enyong Creek

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INTRODUCTION

Enyong Creek drains an inland agricultural catchment of 1300km² as the main surface water running in the south easterly direction that ends at Itu, in Itu Local Government Area, where its confluence is with the larger water body, Cross River. Between its rise near Ehe in Abia state to its mouth at Itu confluence with Cross River in Akwa Ibom state, Nigeria (Fig. 1) is a span of many rural communities with occupation including rice farming and fishing, and crop production and tree plantation. Riparian and upland activities are carried out equally although some, like upland crop farming, are mainly seasonal while riparian farming and fishing go on in all seasons (wet and dry). The wetland farmers, for instance, depend on the water all the time for food and drink. The volume of water swells up to flooding the flood plains in the rainy season (Essien and Sangodoyin, 2006) but shrinks to in-channel flow stage in the dry.

In addition to above, the river is used for navigation for communication between towns and the key coastal markets of the Local Government Areas chiefly; Itu (downstream), Okopedi Use (downstream and Use Ikot Amama (middle) in Ibiono Ibom Local Government Area and Ikpe Ikot Nkon (upstream, in Ini Local Government Area) onigrefill in Akwa Ibom State. Apart from Itu, which is also suburban Local Government Area headquarter carrying on with small-scale service industry and rural market trading in agricultural commodities goods, and commercial transport, all other areas along the course of the river are rural communities with agricultural or forested environment. Therefore pollution sources are particularly agricultural, NPS runoff, faecal wastes from water transporters, water commuters, fishermen and sand-harvesters, and vegetal and animal decays (UN-Water, 2009). However, minor tributary rivulets coming from the upland areas have active interaction with human environment and may contribute pollution load from upland settlements to the main river. Incidences of impure water-related ill health abound and the who i.e. rural

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communities in the three contiguous Local Government Areas do not have any Standard Government Hospital except village health centres and very few private rural medical clinics (AKADEP, 1995). Traditional healers and commercial medicine vendors have their unchecked vocation here. Consequently, the quality of water could be an indicator of water pollution that may affect health of consumers or users, while its quality and quantity may be a constraint to irrigated agriculture in the span of its flood plains (FAO, 1985; Ayers and Wescot, 1989).

Poor quality water, especially one with salinity problem, poses problems to both plants and soil, reducing availability of soil water by creating osmotic effect as would be under drought condition (George, 1983; FAO, 1985); and yield impairment results (George, 1983; Ayers and Wescot, 1989, and Gupta and Gupta, 2008). However, it may not become a serious case under the dilution of the river water by heavy humid rains if it is devoid of saline upland runoff and urban wastewater containing high salinity level (Mateo-Sagasta and Burke, 2010); or if sea water intrusion from tidal fluxes, which occur at some zones on the tributary river, do not reach the upstream farm locations. The case may be different in the dry season if the shrunk in - channel flow stage concentrates salt content in the river. Salinity also degrades soil permeability, creating cultural problems for irrigation. This may decline crop productivity in the clayey-loam wetland soil and, particularly, in the banded plots of swamp rice grown on this wetland. Also, toxicity problems with chemicals like sodium, chlorine, zinc and boron may be injurious to economic crops, thereby producing low crop and water productivity. In some cases, the toxicity problem is transferred to consumers of such crops and fishes.

Therefore, this field study was undertaken to investigate the quality and quantity of Enyong Creek as a source of water supply for conjunctive domestic and irrigation purposes as applied in the numerous riparian communities.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Samples Collection

Enyong Creek lies within Latitudes $8^{\circ}10'1''E$ and $7^{\circ}35'1''$; and Longitude $5^{\circ}25'1''$ and $5^{\circ}10'1''N$, Fig. 1

Water samples were collected at different points or selected reaches along Enyong Creek into standard 2-litre plastic jerry cans. Samples were collected between 8am and 5pm when the river was in active human activities, and replicated between October and March, being the dry season when dependence on its supply was highest with little or no alternative supply source. Altogether 18 samples were delivered to the laboratory for analysis using standard methods. The samples were not subjected to any storage procedure but sub - samples were dispatched immediately on collection to laboratory for microbiological assay, nutrient and heavy metal analysis. Two samples of deionized bottled water (SWAN) were included in the 18 samples for comparison of quality; also one sample was collected from the salt water zone in Eket suspected to be or have intrusion of sea water.

QUALITY ANALYSIS

The analysis was conducted at the river site in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria with full observance of all standards, laws and rules using mostly the Methods for Chemical Analysis of Water and Wastes (EPA, 1974; APHA, 1992). Bacteriological analysis was carried out at the Medical Laboratory for the isolation and identification of *E. coli* and coliform bacteria. Determination of heavy metals was by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry (UNICAM model 939) for Copper, Chromium, Zinc, Nickel, Lead and Manganese, or flame photometry for Potassium and Sodium. However, where there was no lamb, other physical titrimetric and c applied in water sample analysis as follows:

Physical Methods:

Electrical conductivity by conductivity meter

Total suspended solid by filtration and gravimetric method; pH value by electrometric method using pH meter with probe.

Titrimetric Methods:

Calcium and Magnesium and Cadmium by titration with EDTA;
Carbonate and Bicarbonate by Acid titration; Chloride and Cyanide by silver nitrate titration; sulphate by titration with sodium thiosulphate on oxidation of sulphate with potassium iodate (Ademoroti, 1996).

Colorimetric Methods:

Nitrate by Brucine Method
Ammonium nitrogen by Nesslerization method
Phosphate by molybdate blue colour method
Silica by molybdate yellow colour method
Sulphate by turbidimetric method
Phenol by ionic chloride method
Iron by orthophenanthroline method
Boron by the curcumin method

Figure 1: Study Area showing Enyong Creek.

RESULTS

The values of the various quality parameters of the water samples from Enyong Creek are given in Tables 1 and 2. The samples from the study river had approximately similar properties which were slightly different from those of processed and bottled SWAN water, and much different from the sample from Eket which had very

high electrical conductivity and high basic-cation content (Ca, Mg, K and Na). The content indicated that the Eket sample was likely to be sea water. The following heavy metals were not present in Enyong Creek water: Cu, Sb, As, Ba, Hg, Se, and Ag; hence are not included in Table 1.

Table 1: Results of Heavy Metals in Enyong Creek water

Parameter (mg/L)	Okoroma (Gauge)	Nkana bridge	Govt. Farm	Ibiaku Ikot Esifa	Itu (Enyong Creek)	Itu (Cross River)	Swan water	Eket beach (sea water)
Cu	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.25
Fe	0.5	0.71	0.29	0.13	0.21	0.13	0	0.13
Mn	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
B	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.03
Pb	0	0	0	0.006	0	0	0	1.5
Zn	0.26	0.14	0.21	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.21	0.35
Si	0.31	0.81	0.81	0.21	0.41	0.5	1.18	0.59
Cd	0.002	0.007	0.005	0.005	0.007	0.005	0.007	0.009

Table 2: Results of Nutrients and other chemical properties of Enyong Creek water

Parameter	Okoroma (Gauge)	Nkana bridge	Govt. Farm	Ibiaku Ikot Esifa	Itu (Enyong Creek)	Itu (Cross River)	Swan water	Eket beach (sea water)
Acidity	6.53	6.11	6.83	5.96	6.27	6.29	7.05	7.4
Ec (ds/m)	0.035	0.03	0.017	0.006	0.039	0.031	0.133	27.5
CN	0	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03	0	0.04
Ca	1.8	4	4	2	4	6	16	156
Mg	2.2	3.6	9.6	2.4	1.2	1.2	3.6	493.2
K	2.3	6	4.8	2.6	2.4	1.8	2.4	230
Na	0.4	0.6	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	14.4	4800
SAR	0.05	0.07	0.05	0.09	0.09	0.08	0.84	42.16
NO ₃ ⁻	0	0	0	0	0.09	0	0.09	0.22
NH ⁺	0.51	0.78	0.3	0.19	0.38	0.49	1.46	3.3
PO ₄ ⁻	9.1	14.6	11.2	9.6	12.1	14	36.3	6.2
CO ₃ ⁻	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
HCO ₃ ⁻	6.2	0.9	18.3	6.1	24.4	27.5	18.3	91.5
Cl ⁻	10.7	17.8	26.6	14.2	14.2	17.8	26.6	9301
SO ₄ ⁻	10.2	7.5	6.9	6.6	6.6	6.9	6.9	62.4
S ⁻	2.33	1.68	0.2	0.85	1.99	1.87	0.2	3.15
TSS	240	400	0	350	400	450	0	1100
T.H	7	25	55	15	15	20	55	2445

Water Quantity

Here only the minimum flow conditions were considered as they formed the main source of irrigation water during the dry season. The minimum stage and corresponding discharge were as follows:

At upstream gauging station, Okoroma, stage = 11.34m, discharge = 3.93m³/s.

At upper gauging station, Ikpe Ikot Nkon, stage = 2.31m, discharge = 8.94m³/s.

At middle gauging station, Nkana, stage =6.53m, discharge = 12.50m³/s

The minimum quantity available would consider the uses for fishing and water transportation to arrive at how much irrigable area can be accommodated without making the basin a closed water resource system in dry season.

DISCUSSION

In discussing the qualities of the water samples it was necessary to relate the qualities to the intended use of the water; in this respect, the use is for domestic and for irrigation purposes.

CONSIDERATION FOR DOMESTIC PURPOSES

The pH values of the water samples ranged from 5.43 to 7.40 (Table 1). All the water samples from the Study Area have values below 6.5 except the sample from the Government Farm where swamp rice is grown. The SWAN water and the Eket sample have values above 7.0. The permissible pH range for domestic purposes given by WHO is 6.5 – 9.2. This means that all samples from the Project Area have values outside the permissible range, being too acidic in reaction. In view of this, Enyong Creek water along its reach would not, theoretically, be considered suitable for consumption. The acidic water may enhance metal dissolution.

Regarding the pH value of the water samples, the two Swan water samples, the sample from the Government Farm and the one from Eket would be considered quite potable but the high salt content or excessive total hardness of the sample from Eket makes that sample highly not potable. The high value of electrical conductivity (Ec) indicates that the water from Eket is very saline while all others which have very low Ec values are soft and therefore good for domestic use in this respect.

The nutrients and the trace element contents were generally low in the water samples and in most cases were below the highest desirable or permissible limits set by the World Health Organization (WHO) for drinking water standards. However, a number of samples contained high levels of Fe, particularly the Nwaniba sample which had a content of 1.04 mg/l which value was a little higher than 1.0mg/l which is the maximum permissible level given by WHO (1984).

The bacteriological standard was quite poor in many of the samples. About 70% of the samples had *E. coli* and about 20% had coliform organisms which suggest the presence of decaying waste from the area. The presence of *E. coli* makes the sample not quite suitable for domestic purposes. The water would require treatment to eliminate the pathogenic organisms in order to make it potable.

CONSIDERATION FOR IRRIGATION PURPOSES

All the water samples were good for use in irrigation except the sample from Eket. The water samples from the Enyong creek have low electrical conductivity values and therefore low salinity hazards. Thus, the salinity or sea water presence indicated in Eket sample had no upstream intrusion to this tributary river. They were also low in sodium content and therefore low in sodium hazards. They are therefore put in low salinity and low sodium hazard class (CI – SI) using USDA classification system. They have electrical conductivity (EC) less than 0.25 milli-Siemens/cm and Sodium Adsorption Ratio (SAR) less than 10. (FAO, 1985; Bhattacharya and Michael, 2003).

The water from Eket was not suitable for irrigation because of high EC which is 27.5 milli-Siemens/cm and high sodium hazard with SAR greater than 26, it would be put in the very high salinity and very high sodium hazard class (C4 –S4). Hence it was not suitable for irrigation. The trace elements in all the samples were much below the FAO recommended maximum concentrations for irrigation water. Their concentrations in the water would not adversely affect the growth of plants or the fertility of the soils. (FAO, 1994, Gupta and Gupta, 2008). They are below the toxic levels as given by FAO (1994).

SUMMARY

The water samples from Enyong creek were found to have acidity levels exceeding the limit recommended by WHO and Federal Environmental Protection Agency (FEPA, 1991) for potable water. In other aspects, however, the water was found to be of good quality. The samples contained no excessive nutrients or heavy metals at the toxic levels going by WHO and FEPA guidelines. A good number of them contained pathogenic bacteria, *E. coli*, a situation that requires some treatment or purification before the water could be used for domestic purposes.

For irrigation purposes, all the samples were found to be of excellent quality. They were non-saline and had very low sodium concentrations. They would not therefore impose any salinity or sodium hazards on the soils or crops grown in the soils. The samples also had no toxic levels of heavy metals.

The SWAN (bottled) water samples were found to be of high quality. They had pH values within the recommended range, low contents of nutrients and heavy metals and no pathogenic organisms.

The water designated 'Eket' (Table 1) was neither potable nor good for irrigation. It had high contents of chloride, sodium, and total hardness much beyond the limits set by WHO and FEPA. The high salinity and excessive sodium concentration make it unsuitable for irrigation purposes.

CONCLUSION

The water quality contributes towards a favourable environment for rice and vegetable growing in the tributary swamp land drained by Enyong Creek; and was satisfactory for irrigation but questionable for domestic use. Treatment is needed for domestic use. As for the water quantity, this aspect can only be evaluated after a more precise identification of development options in the study area. If necessary this will be studied where suitable irrigation schemes with their main supply from the river have been identified.

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